

2024	Fauna Balkana University of Novi Sad, Serbia	Volume 5 pp 151-156
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A new species in the genus *Dalmatoreicheia* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005 from Peloponnese (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Scaritinae)

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SUMMARY. *Dalmatoreicheia karamani* sp. nov. from Greece (S Peloponnese) is described, illustrated including its aedeagus; and is compared with both to date known species of the genus.

KEY WORDS: description, Greece, Reicheiina, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The anophthalmous Reicheiina genus *Dalmatoreicheia* was described by Magrini and Bulirsch (2005) in a single female from Biokovo Mt. in Croatia (Dalmatia), later Bulirsch and Guéorguiev (2008) established *D. maderi* from Albania. Recently our colleague I. Karaman found in Southern Peloponnese two specimens which belong to this genus as well.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study of dry-mounted specimens, including measurements and examination of microsculpture, was done at a magnification up to 98×. Aedeagus of holotype was fixed in Euparal and placed on the same pin below the beetle. Measurements: length of body is measured from the anterior margin of the closed mandibles to the apex of the elytra along the suture; length of the pronotum along its midline; width of the pronotum at widest point; length of the elytra from its base to its apex along the suture; width of the elytra at its widest point. Length of body is given with 0.05 mm accuracy; other measurements including ratios and means are

rounded to two decimal places. Label locality data are quoted verbatim except standardized dates.

Habitus image was taken with a Canon EOS 700D camera in combination with a Canon MP-E65 1-5x macro lens. Images of aedeagus and parameres were made using an above mentioned camera mounted on a Motic BA 410E-T compound microscope in transmitted light. Resulting images were focus stacked using Zerene Stacker and then postprocessed in Paint.Net, Paint, XnView and Live Photogallery.

For comparison of a new *Dalmatoreicheia* species were studied single holotypes of both to date known species as well as most species of all genera of Balkan Reicheiina from the first authors collection as well as loaned from diverse museums.

The following abbreviations are used to indicate the depository of specimens:

CDP Dragan Pavićević private collection, Belgrade, Serbia;

PBPC Petr Bulirsch collection, Prague, Czech Republic.

Other abbreviations:

SP: setiferous puncture(s); BSP: basal setiferous puncture(s); DSP: dorsal setiferous puncture(s); HT: holotype(s); /, // by locality labels: end of line, label.

RESULTS

Genus Dalmatoreicheia Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005

Type species: *Dalmatoreicheia janaki* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005.

Dalmatoreicheia karamani sp. nov. (Figs 1-9)

TYPE MATERIAL. Holotype (♂): Greece, Peloponnese, Mani, Gytheo, Platanos, 18.04.2022, I. Karaman leg., (CDP). Paratype: (1 ♂) with the same data as HT, (PBPC).

DESCRIPTION. Habitus as in Fig. 1. Body rusty red-brown, legs very slightly, antennae slightly lighter, mouthparts yellowish. Length 3.05 mm in HT and 2.90 mm in PT.

Head. Moderately broad, neck broad; anterior margin of clypeus between distinctly protruding, rather sharp lateral lobes very slightly emarginated; impressions of clypeus oblique, broad and moderately deep, longitudinal carina short and broad. Genal posterior angles moderately broadly rounded; strongly vaulted supraantennal plates separated from genae by deep and narrow furrow; carina of prolonged supraantennal plates long and sharp. Eyes absent, genae moderately strongly, regularly vaulted. Vertex almost regularly, moderately deeply reticulated. Antennae

Figs 1-9. *Dalmatoreicheia karamani* sp. nov., HT: 1, habitus; 2, pronotal outline; 3, elytral humero-lateral outline; 4, right hind tibia with tarsi; 5, median lobe of aedeagus in ventro-lateral view; 6, median lobe of aedeagus in right lateral view; 7-8, parameri; 9, urite.

with antennomere 2 long, about as long as 3 and 4 combined, antennomeres 6-8 moniliform, 9-10 barely longer than broad.

Pronotum (Figs. 1-2). In lateral view below its middle part not concave, surface moderately shiny, with almost regular, fine isodiametric reticulation; in HT 1.07, in PT 1.09 times as wide long as, in HT 1.49, in PT 1.46 times as wide as head, widest in about midlength; outline regularly, rather strongly rounded. Reflexed lateral margin entire, extended from sharp, slightly protruded anterior angles to base, thin in latero-basal part and above flange; posterior angles very broadly rounded; lateral channel narrow, with anterior and posterior pair of lateral SP, both slightly moved from lateral channel inside; with neither sublateral nor submedial SP. Median line distinctly impressed, deeper posteriorly and reaching basal furrow, anterior transverse impression broad and superficial, medially almost indistinct. Basal part (flange) small, barely produced posteriorly. Proepisterna narrowly visible from above in apical half.

Elytra (Figs. 1, 3). Slightly long ovate, disc moderately flattened in lateral view, in HT 1.65, in PT 1.64 times as long as wide, in HT 1.27, in PT 1.31 times as wide as pronotum, in HT 2.25, in PT 2.29 times as long as pronotum; surface rather shiny, with irregular rests of fine reticulation, latter slightly more distinct latero-apically; base slightly sloping to moderately broadly rounded, rather protruded humeri; outline slightly broadened on sides, in middle third almost parallel; lateral channel broad, slightly broadened apically, anteriorly reaching interval 5, its margin (Fig. 3) with 8-10 rather sharp and long humero-lateral teeth and below them with several blunt, very small and long denticles up to about posterior third; elytra broadest just below midlength; suture barely depressed at base. Base without tubercle, with deep BSP. Elytral striae 1-5 rather deep, 6 slightly, 7 distinctly finer, rather roughly punctured, latero-basally shortened just below base; postero-laterally on apex. Intervals basally rather strongly vaulted, latero-apically slightly flattened. Intervals 3, 5 and 7 with rows of 18-12 SP with long setae.

Legs: Anterior tibiae with terminal tooth bent outwards and downwards; lower lateral tooth large and moderately sharp, upper much smaller and rather blunt. Hind tibiae and tarsi as in Fig. 4.

Aedeagus (Figs 5-8). Length in HT 0.53 mm; median lobe in lateral view as in Fig. 6, narrow, outline almost regularly rounded, apex very long and subparallel, moderately strongly bent down, tip moderately narrowly rounded; apical part in ventral view as in Fig. 5. Urite as in Fig. 9; parameres as in Figs 7-8, bisetose.

Stylomeres. Unknown.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Dalmatoreicheia karamani* sp. nov. has the body relatively large, the head and the pronotum distinctly reticulated; the head without the eye remnants and the clypeus with the oblique impressions broad and rather deep,

prolonged by the short, rather blunt longitudinal keel; the pronotum with the outline distinctly convex, with neither sublateral nor submedial SP; the moderately long elytra with numerous humero-lateral teeth and basally with rather deep and regular striae 1-7 with rough punctuation.

It can be distinguished from *D. janaki* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005 by the body being slightly larger; by the head having the antennae shorter; by the elytra being more ovate, having more protruded humeri and by SP only in intervals 3, 5 and 7, not in 2. *D. karamani* sp. nov. differs from *D. maderi* Bulirsch and Guéorguiev, 2008 by the body being slightly smaller; by the head having the antennae shorter; by the elytra being more ovate, having more protruded humeri, more vaulted inner intervals; by SP being only in intervals 3, 5 and 7 not in 2, 4 and 6, and finally, by the very different shape of the median lobe of the aedeagus (in *D. maderi* is the median lobe much shorter and broader, with short and broad apex (as in Bulirsch and Guéorguiev (2008): fig. 7).

ETYMOLOGY. Patronymic, after our colleague, zoologist, Ivo Karaman from the Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia, discoverer of this new species.

DISTRIBUTION AND BIONOMY. The new species is known only from the type locality in S Peloponnese. Both specimen were collected from MSS by sifting a ground in deciduous forest with north exposition at steep slope above the periodical creek.

CONCLUSION

Dalmatoreicheia karamani sp. nov. is the third known species of the anophthalmous genus *Dalmatoreicheia*. To date this genus has been known in two species (both described in a single HT) from Croatia (Dalmatia) and Albania so that finding of two specimens in very south Peloponnese has been a bit unexpected and distinctly expands the area of this genus occurrence. According to Bulirsch and Guéorguiev (2008), Guéorguiev (2007) and Arndt *et al.* (2011) the nearest *Reicheiina* species occur in Greek mainland and in Ionian Islands and belong to the genus *Reicheadella* Reitter, 1913. The new species can be easily distinguished from all species of this genus as well as of the genus *Chaetomargoreicheia* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005 by the absence of the sublateral and / or submedial SP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are very thankful to Ivo Karaman who gave us such interesting new species as well as to Jiří Janák (Rtyně nad Bílinou, Czech Republic) for preparing of the figures.

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